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PRAGMATIC AND FUNCTIONAL EQUIVALENCE OF WRITTEN TRANSLATION

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Abstract: *This article explores the crucial concept of pragmatic and functional equivalence in written translation, emphasizing the need to go beyond literal word-for-word translation to convey the intended meaning and impact of the source text. It analyzes the various factors influencing the achievement of these two types of equivalence, including cultural context, intended audience, and communicative purpose. The paper investigates how pragmatic equivalence, focusing on the intended effect and communicative function of the text, and functional equivalence, aiming for a comparable effect on the target audience, can be effectively achieved through strategic translation techniques. By examining real-world examples and theoretical frameworks, the article sheds light on the complexities and importance of achieving both pragmatic and functional equivalence in written translation, contributing to a deeper understanding of successful cross-cultural communication through written texts.*

Key words: *Written translation, Pragmatic equivalence, Functional equivalence, translation theory, Cross cultural communication.*

When we translate something from one language to another, it's not just about changing the words. We also have to think about the situation and what the speaker really means to say—this is what we call the context and pragmatics of language. "The aim of translation is to produce a text that is functionally equivalent to the source text, that is, a text that has the same effect on the target reader as the source text had on the source reader¹. «They can really affect how we choose our words and grammar in translation. First, about context. This is all about where and when something is being said, and who is saying it. For example, if two friends are talking casually, they might use short sentences and slang. But if one of those friends is giving a speech, they would use longer sentences and more formal words. So, when we translate, we need to know the context to pick the right words and grammar. If we do not, we might make the translation sound too formal or too casual². Now, pragmatics is about understanding what people mean, even when they don't say it directly. For instance, if someone says, «It's chilly in here, » they might actually be asking for the window to be closed without saying it directly. So, when we translate, we have to do more than just look at the words; we have to think about what the speaker wants to happen or what they really feel. Let's see how this works with an example. Imagine we're translating a story from English to Uzbek where a character says, "Could you possibly open the window?" In English, this is a polite way to ask for the window to be opened. But in Uzbek, maybe they would just say it more directly. So, the translation would need to make sure it sounds polite in Uzbek too. Sometimes, the grammar itself

¹ Baker, M. (2011). In other words: A coursebook on translation. Routledge; 134p

² https://proz.com/kudoz/english_to_french/translation_tips/14220-the_importance_of_grammar_in_translation.html

can show politeness or respect. In some languages, like Korean or Japanese, there are different words and grammar for talking to someone older or more important. But in English, we use the same words for everyone. So, when translating to or from these languages, we need to change the grammar to match the level of respect. Also, some things we say in one language don't really make sense in another because of the culture. For example, in English, people might say «Break a leg» to wish someone good luck, but if we translate that directly into another language, it might sound like you want them to actually break their leg! So, we have to find a way to say «good luck» that makes sense in the other language. In short, understanding context and pragmatics means we have to think about more than just words. We have to consider who is talking, who they are talking to, what the situation is, and what they really mean to say. And then we use grammar and words in the translation that fit all of that. It's a big job, and it's really important to make sure that the translation sounds just right and that it says what the original speaker meant.

In translation, "Functional equivalence is achieved when the translation communicates the same message as the original text, but in a way that is appropriate for the target audience and culture³." functional equivalence aims to convey the intended meaning and purpose of the original text, rather than translating each word literally. It focuses on matching the function, style, and impact of the source and target texts. This is especially important for texts with a specific purpose, such as legal documents or marketing materials. "The concept of functional equivalence is crucial to understanding how translation works in different contexts⁴." To achieve functional equivalence, translators need to understand the context and purpose of the original text, as well as the cultural and linguistic background of the target audience. They should also consider factors like the tone, formality, and genre of the text. Here are some examples of functional equivalence in English-to-Uzbek translation:

- Translating idioms and figurative language: Instead of translating idioms word-for-word, translators find culturally appropriate equivalents that convey the same meaning. For example, the English idiom «kick the bucket» might be translated into the Uzbek “chelakni tepmoq” literally, it really means to die.
- Adapting cultural references: Translators modify cultural references that may not be familiar to the target audience. For instance, a reference to Thanksgiving in an English text might be replaced with a reference to “Navro’z”, a traditional Uzbek holiday.
- Adjusting sentence structure and word order: Translators may need to change the sentence structure or word order to fit the grammar and style of the target language. For example, English sentences often use active voice, while Uzbek sentences often use passive voice.
- Modifying the level of formality: Translators adjust the formality of the target text to suit the intended audience. A formal business letter in English might be translated into a more informal style in Uzbek if it's meant for a general audience.

Functional equivalence is a key concept in translation. "Functional equivalence is a matter of degree, and it is often difficult to achieve perfect equivalence between source and target texts⁵." By prioritizing the meaning and purpose of the original text, translators can create target texts that are

³ Newmark, P. (1988). A textbook of translation. Prentice Hall; 62p

⁴ Snell-Hornby, M. (2006). Translation studies: An integrated approach. John Benjamins Publishing;165p

⁵ House, J. (1997). Translation quality assessment: A model revisited. Routledge;55p

effective and appropriate for the target audience⁶. Functional equivalence is crucial in translating idioms because idiomatic expressions are often deeply rooted in cultural nuances and context that may not directly translate between languages. Idioms typically convey meanings that extend beyond the literal definitions of the individual words they contain. Here's why functional equivalence is important for idioms:

- **Preserves Meaning:** Functional equivalence focuses on conveying the underlying meaning of the idiom rather than the literal words, which often don't make sense when translated directly.
- **Maintains Cultural Relevance:** Many idioms are based on cultural references that are specific to a particular language or culture. Functional equivalence helps to find an idiom in the target language that carries a similar cultural significance and meaning.
- **Ensures Comprehension:** Translating idioms literally can confuse the reader if the literal translation doesn't exist or have the same connotation in the target language. Functional equivalence makes sure that the intended message is clearly understood.
- **Retains Impact:** Idioms often have an emotional or rhetorical impact—like humor, irony, or emphasis—that can be lost in a literal translation. Functional equivalence aims to retain the same impact in the target language.
- **Reflects Language Usage:** Idiomatic expressions are a natural part of spoken and written language; thus, using functionally equivalent idioms in translation helps to reflect natural language usage and makes the text more relatable and engaging for the target audience.
- **Avoids Misinterpretation:** Without functional equivalence, idioms can be misinterpreted, potentially altering the intended message and leading to misunderstandings.

In essence, functional equivalence is about finding a translation that functions the same way in the target language as the original does in the source language, creating a translation that feels natural and conveys the same message, tone, and intent.

Functional equivalence, also known as dynamic equivalence, in translation focuses on conveying the same meaning and effect as the source text in the target language, even if this requires departing from a word-for-word translation. Here are a few examples where functional equivalence is applied:

- Idioms and Expressions:
 - ✓ English: «Break a leg!»
 - ✓ Literal Translation: «Bir oyoğunu kır!» (Turkish)
 - ✓ Functional Equivalence: «İyi şanslar!» (Good luck!)
- The literal translation would convey an entirely different meaning in Turkish, possibly a wish for harm. The functionally equivalent translation captures the intended meaning of wishing luck.
- Proverbs:
 - ✓ Spanish: «Más vale tarde que nunca.»

⁶https://www.researchgate.net/publication/349476714_Grammatical_Features_Of_The_Translation_Based_On_The_Number_Category_Of_The_Noun

- ✓ Literal Translation: «Better late than never.»
- ✓ Functional Equivalence: «Il vaut mieux tard que jamais.» (French)
- This proverb exists with the same function in both languages, so the translation maintains the original proverb's wisdom and effect.
- Cultural Concepts:
- ✓ Japanese: «お疲れ様です» (Otsukaresama desu)
- ✓ Literal Translation: «You are tired.»
- ✓ Functional Equivalence: «Good job!» or «Thanks for your hard work!»
- The literal translation doesn't capture the cultural nuance of acknowledging someone's effort and work, which the functionally equivalent translations do.
- Slogans and Marketing:
- ✓ English: «Finger-lickin' good» (KFC slogan)
- ✓ Literal Translation in Chinese might imply an unpleasant action.
- ✓ Functional Equivalence: «吮指原味鸡» (Tastes good to the last finger)
- The functional equivalence maintains the slogan's appeal and intent without a direct word-for-word translation which might not resonate culturally or may be misunderstood.
- Titles and Names:
- ✓ English: «Harry Potter and the Philosopher's Stone»
- ✓ Literal Translation: «Harri Potter va falsafa toshi» (Uzbek)
- ✓ Functional Equivalence: «Harry Potter and the Sorcerer's Stone» (American English)

The name of the book was changed to match the American audience's more familiar concept of a «sorcerer» rather than a «philosopher,» thus maintaining the function and appeal of the title. In each of these examples, the focus of functional equivalence is less on the precise lexical correspondence and more on the impact and understanding that the original text has for its audience. It's about recreating the same experience and response that the source text aims to evoke.

Here are more examples of English idioms and how they might be translated into Uzbek using functional equivalence to ensure that the meaning and intent are preserved:

- English Idiom: «Out of the blue.»
- ✓ Literal Translation: «Ko'kdan tushib qoldi.»
- ✓ Functional Equivalence: «Tomdan tarasha tushganday.» (Came unexpectedly)
- English Idiom: «To kill two birds with one stone.»
- ✓ Literal Translation: «Ikki qushni bir tosh bilan o'ldirmoq.»
- ✓ Functional Equivalence: «Bir o'q bilan ikkita quyonni o'ldirmoq.» (to get two things done with the help of a single action)
- English Idiom: «Miss the boat.»

- ✓ Literal Translation: «kemani o'tkazib yubormoq»
- ✓ Functional Equivalence: «Poyezd o'tib ketdi.» (To be too late)
- English Idiom: «Burn the midnight oil.»
- ✓ Literal Translation: «Yarim tunning yog'ini yoqmoq.»
- ✓ Functional Equivalence: «Kechgacha ishlamoq.» (To work until late at night)
- English Idiom: «When pigs fly.»
- ✓ Literal Translation: «Cho'chqalar uchganida.» (This direct translation would sound absurd in Uzbek)
- ✓ Functional Equivalence: «Tuyani dumi yerga tekkanda.» (It will never happen)
- English Idiom: «white as a sheet.»
- ✓ Literal Translation: «varoqdek oqargan.»
- ✓ Functional Equivalence: «Arvohek oqarib ketgan.» (Their face is very pale, usually because of illness, shock or fear)
- English Idiom: «Cost an arm and a leg.»
- ✓ Literal Translation: «Qo'l va oyoqcha turmoq.»
- ✓ Functional Equivalence: «Otni kallasidek» (To be very expensive)
- English Idiom: «Don't judge a book by its cover.»
- ✓ Literal Translation: «Kitobni muqovasiga qarab baholamang.»
- ✓ Functional Equivalence: «Tashqi ko'rinishga qarab baho bermang.» (Don't be deceived by appearances)

The fields of pragmatics and functional equivalence lie at the heart of written translation, representing the deeper levels of meaning and contextual use of language that go beyond mere literal words. Pragmatics is concerned with how meaning is constructed in context, considering factors such as the speaker's intention, the relationship between speaker and listener, and the situational circumstances. Functional equivalence, on the other hand, focuses on achieving the same effect in the target language as the source language intended, ensuring that the translation fulfills the same function for its new audience as the original did for its own. Translators must grapple with the challenge of conveying not just the semantic content of a text but also its pragmatic nuances, which often involve cultural connotations, implied meanings, irony, or humor. They strive to produce a translation that is functionally equivalent, meaning that the reader in the target culture will understand and react to the text in the same way the source culture's reader would. This requires a deep understanding of both cultures and the ability to creatively reconstruct the message in a way that preserves its original intent and resonance. One example of the importance of pragmatics and functional equivalence is in the translation of a joke. A literal translation might render the joke nonsensical or unfunny in another language. Instead, the translator needs to find a way to recreate the humor in a culturally appropriate manner, which might involve changing the joke's setup or punchline to something more relevant and understandable to the target audience. In conclusion, pragmatics and functional equivalence are indispensable in written translation. They are what enable translations to go beyond being mere copies of source texts, transforming them into

living documents that breathe and speak within the target culture. A successful translation is one that captures the spirit of the original—its tone, its nuances, and its unspoken implications—allowing the translated text to function effectively within the linguistic and cultural framework of its new audience. It is the translator's skill in balancing these elements that ultimately allows the act of translation to be not just an exchange of words, but an exchange of meaning, culture, and understanding.

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